

In Silico: Prediction of the Antihypertensive Mechanism of Papaya Leaf Extract via β_1 Adrenergic Receptor and Phenylalanine Hydrolase Inhibition

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Abstract

In previous research, the leaves of the papaya (*Carica papaya*) have demonstrated potential as an antihypertensive drug. However, research on papaya leaves as an antihypertensive treatment is still rare, especially on its inhibition mechanism of β_1 adrenergic receptor and phenylalanine hydrolase receptor. Hence, in silico studies were performed to examine molecularly at the bonding of active substances of papaya leaves with the target proteins. Molecular docking in silico studies were used to examine the free binding energy affinity ΔG and amino acid residue similarity of inhibition mechanism through β_1 adrenergic receptor (code: 7BVQ) and phenylalanine hydrolase receptor (code: 6PAH) to the control carazolol and L-dopa as well as the active substance of the leaves of the papaya. The free bond energy (ΔG) and percentage of amino acid residue equation of active compounds of papaya leaves on β_1 adrenergic receptor were myricetin (ΔG -9.3 kcal/mol, amino acid residue equation 66%), linoleic acid (-6.8, 66%) and ferulic acid (-7.6, 66%). As for phenylalanine hydrolase receptor the values of carpaine (ΔG -8.5 kcal/mol, amino acid residue equation 0%) were obtained. The antihypertensive mechanism of papaya leaves could be mediated by β_1 adrenergic receptor because the affinity level of its active substances of its active substances to β_1 adrenergic receptor greater than phenylalanine hydrolase receptor.

Keywords: Anti-hypertensive; *Carica papaya*; in silico; β_1 adrenergic receptor; phenylalanine hydrolase receptor

Introduction

Hypertension is the second cardiovascular system disease that many people suffer from in the world [1]. Based on reported global data, an estimated 1.39 billion people in the world suffer from hypertension, of which two thirds are in low-middle income countries. Hypertension is a condition where systolic blood pressure is ≥ 140 mmHg and diastolic ≥ 90 mmHg when blood pressure measurements have been carried out twice and the results are not much different [8].

Hypertension can occur due to system disorders in the body, namely the sympathetic nervous system, renin-angiotensin-aldosterone (RAAS), and blood vessels. Based on the pathomechanism of hypertension, there are several target proteins that play a role. Of the various proteins involved, two target proteins were chosen to be studied in this research, namely β_1 adrenergic and PAH enzymes. Based on the pathophysiology of hypertension, these two proteins are believed to inhibit the process of hypertension by inhibiting the increase in heart contractions. Inhibition of β_1 adrenergic receptors can prevent when the body needs blood supply, the heart fulfills this supply by activating the sympathetic nervous system and catecholamines will stimulate it to increase the performance of heart muscle contraction and cardiac output [9]. Phenylalanine hydroxylase (PAH) works to convert phenylalanine into tyrosine and tyrosine is converted again into L-DOPA by tyrosine hydroxylase. Then, L-DOPA is converted into norepinephrine by dopamine 6-hydroxylase. Norepinephrine is a vasoconstrictor that circulates in the blood circulation and will work in the muscle blood vessels, producing a vasoconstrictive effect on the blood vessels [4]. If this series of physiological activities occurs excessively for a long time, it will result in hypertension.

Hypertension treatment aims to reduce cardiovascular complications and lower blood pressure. Hypertension treatment can be done with non-pharmacotherapy therapy such as lifestyle modification as the first line and pharmacotherapy as the second line [14]. Limited use of drugs due to side effects of drugs in pharmacological therapy means it is necessary to develop drugs from active compounds as prevention or alternative and supportive treatment for hypertension.

In Indonesia, many plants are found that are efficacious and can be used as herbal plants. One example of this plant is papaya with the Latin name *Carica papaya*. In several journals and articles, it was found that papaya leaves have antihypertensive potential because they contain several groups of active compounds including primary and secondary metabolites. Active compounds in papaya leaves that have the potential to act as antihypertensives include benzyl isothiocyanate, carpain, myristic acid, myosmine, and nicotine [13]. However, research on papaya leaves as an antihypertensive through inhibiting β 1 adrenergic receptors and the phenylalanine hydroxylase (PAH) enzyme has not been widely carried out.

This research aims to determine the potential of the active compounds contained in papaya leaves in preventing hypertension using in silico research methods by inhibiting β 1 adrenergic receptors and the enzyme phenylalanine hydroxylase (PAH). The in silico approach is carried out using molecular docking, namely computational learning of the ligand or drug that will bind to the target protein. This research consists of 2 stages, namely the first stage aims to determine the mechanism of active compounds in papaya leaves in inhibiting β 1 adrenergic receptors and PAH enzymes in silico using the molecular docking method. The second stage aims to predict the physicochemical, pharmacokinetic and toxicity parameters of the active compounds in papaya leaves when given orally.

Materials and Methods

Molecular docking in silico studies were used to examine the free binding energy affinity ΔG and amino acid residue similarity of inhibition mechanism through β 1 adrenergic receptor (code: 7BVQ) and phenylalanine hydroxylase receptor (code: 6PAH) to the control carazolol and L-dopa as well as the active substance of the leaves of the papaya. The compound was obtained from the PubChem ([Link](#)) server with a recorded CID.

This research consists of 2 stages, namely the first stage aims to determine the mechanism of active compounds in papaya leaves in inhibiting β 1 adrenergic receptors and PAH enzymes in silico using the molecular docking method. The docking application used is PyRx 0.8 with the Vina autodock system because it can be used for free, easy and open to the public, which is distributed under the Simplified BSD license [10]. Next, the results of the molecular docking are entered into the Biovia Discovery Studio Visualizer 2016 application to see the presence of ligand interactions in the results of the molecular docking of the resulting compounds.

Second stage aims to predict the physicochemical, pharmacokinetic and toxicity parameters of the active compounds in papaya leaves when given orally. Predictions were carried out using PkCSM Online Tools software. PkCSM Online Tools application is used because it does not cost anything and can display complete ADMET results and is easy to use [11].

Results and Conclusion

Potential Analysis of the *Carica Papaya* Leaves Active Compound as β 1 Adrenergic Protein Inhibitors with In Silico Method

The value of the docking results between Carazolol control and β 1 adrenergic protein in Table 1 shows a ΔG value of -9.7 kcal/mol and the total amino acid residues obtained are 9, namely SER1228, ASN1363, ASP1138, TYR1367 PHE1341, PHE1218, VAL1139, VAL1142, and TRP1134. Next, a comparison of the docking results was carried out between the ligand, namely the active compound from papaya leaves (*Carica papaya*) and β 1 adrenergic protein.

Based on the free energy indicator (ΔG) and the percentage of amino acid residues, it was found that active compounds in papaya leaves have an affinity for β 1 adrenergic protein, namely rutin, luteolin, and genistein. The results of docking the active compounds of papaya (*Carica papaya*) molecules against β 1 adrenergic receptors can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Analysis of inhibiting potency of *Carica papaya* leaves active compounds against β 1 adrenergic protein receptor with in silico method

Compound	CID	Binding affinity (kcal/mol)	Similarity of bonds amino acid residues (%)
Human Beta 1 Adrenergic Receptor bound to Carazolol (Native Ligan)		-9.7	9/9 (100%)
Rutin	5280805	-11.6	5/9 (55.5%)
Luteolin	5280445	-9.9	4/9 (44.4%)
Genistein	5280961	-9.8	5/9 (55.5%)
Naringenin	439246	-9.8	3/9 (33.3%)
Myricetin	5281672	-9.3	6/9 (66.6%)
Kaempferol	5280863	-9.2	3/9 (33.3%)
Quercetin	5280343	-9.2	5/9 (55.5%)
Epicatechin	72276	-9.1	5/9 (55.5%)
Ferulic acid	445858	-7.6	6/9 (66.6%)
Caffeic-acid	689043	-7.5	2/9 (22.2%)
P-coumaric acid	637542	-7.4	4/9 (44.4%)
Alpha ionone	5282108	-7.1	3/9 (33.3%)
Chymopapain	9002	-7.0	4/9 (44.4%)
Linoleic-acid	5280450	-6.8	6/9 (66.6%)
Oleic-acid	445639	-6.5	3/9 (33.3%)
Myristic-acid	11005	-6.4	5/9 (55.5%)
Gallic acid	370	-6.4	3/9 (33.3%)
Nicotine	89594	-6.4	5/9 (55.5%)
Palmitic-acid	985	-6.3	4/9 (44.4%)
Lauric-acid	3893	-6.1	5/9 (55.5%)
Ascorbic-acid	54670067	-6.0	1/9 (11.1%)
Niacin	938	-5.6	3/9 (33.3%)
Carpaine	442630	-3.9	0/9 (0%)

Visualization of Intermolecular Interactions between Active Compounds in Papaya Leaves (*Carica papaya*) and β 1 Adrenergic Protein

Figure 1. Carazolol- β 1 adrenergic. Carazolol binds to the binding site SER1228, ASN1363, ASP1138, TYR1367, PHE1341, PHE1218, VAL1139, VAL1142, and TRP1134

Figure 2. Rutin- β 1 adrenergic. Rutin binds to the binding site PHE1218, ASP1138, VAL1139, PHE1341, and VAL1142.

Potential Analysis of the *Carica Papaya* Leaves Active Compound as PAH enzyme with In Silico Method

The value of the docking results between the L-DOPA control and PAH enzyme in Table 2 shows a value of ΔG -6.5 kcal/mol and the total amino acid residues obtained are 5, namely PHE254, PRO281, HIS290, TYR325, GLU330 bonds. Next, the docking results are compared. between the ligand, namely the active compound from papaya leaves (*Carica papaya*) and PAH enzyme. Based on the free energy indicator (ΔG) and the percentage of amino acid residues, no active compounds in papaya leaves were found to have affinity for PAH enzyme. The value of the results of docking the active compounds of papaya (*Carica papaya*) molecules against the PAH enzyme receptor can be seen in Table 2.

Visualization of Intermolecular Interactions between Active Compounds in Papaya Leaves (*Carica papaya*) and Phenylalanine Hydroxylase Enzyme

Figure 3. L-DOPA-PAH enzyme. L-DOPA binds to the binding site PHE254, PRO281, HIS290, TYR325, GLU330.

Figure 4. Naringenin-PAH enzyme. Naringenin does not bind to any binding site.

Table 2. Analysis of inhibiting potency of *Carica papaya* leaves active compounds against PAH enzyme with in silico method

Compound	CID	Binding affinity (kcal/mol)	Similarity of bonds amino acid residues (%)
Human Phenylalanine Hydroxylase Catalytic domain dimer with bound L-Dopa (3,4-Dihydroxyphenylalanine) inhibitor (Native Ligan)		-6.5	5/5 (100%)
Naringenin	439246	-9.9	0/5 (0%)
Kaempferol	5280863	-9.9	0/5 (0%)
Quercetin	5280343	-9.7	0/5 (0%)
Luteolin	5280445	-9.6	0/5 (0%)
Genistein	5280961	-9.2	0/5 (0%)
Epicatechin	72276	-9.2	0/5 (0%)
Myricetin	5281672	-9.2	0/5 (0%)
Rutin	5280805	-9.2	0/5 (0%)
Carpaine	442630	-8.5	0/5 (0%)
Alpha ionone	5282108	-7.4	0/5 (0%)
Chymopapain	9002	-7.0	0/5 (0%)
Caffeic-acid	689043	-7.0	0/5 (0%)
Ferulic acid	445858	-6.9	0/5 (0%)
Oleic-acid	445639	-6.7	0/5 (0%)
Linoleic-acid	5280450	-6.6	0/5 (0%)
P-coumaric acid	637542	-6.5	0/5 (0%)
Myristic-acid	11005	-6.2	0/5 (0%)
Palmitic-acid	985	-6.2	0/5 (0%)
Gallic acid	370	-6.1	0/5 (0%)
Niacin	938	-6.1	0/5 (0%)
Nicotine	89594	-6.0	0/5 (0%)
Lauric-acid	3893	-5.7	0/5 (0%)
Ascorbic-acid	54670067	-5.5	0/5 (0%)

Prediction Results Physicochemical Properties of Active Compounds Papaya Leaf Extract (*Carica papaya*) with swissADME Online Tool

Based on the results of the physicochemical predictions of 23 active compounds of *Carica papaya* in Table 3, it was found that active compounds fulfilled the Lipinski rule of five criteria, namely the flavonoids naringenin, kaempferol, luteolin, myricetin, quercetin, genistein, and epicatechin. There are two active compounds that do not fulfill the Lipinski rules. The active compounds are the carpain alkaloid group and the routine flavonoid group.

Prediction of the physicochemical properties of active compounds was carried out on 23 active compounds. The predicted results of the physicochemical properties of the nine active compounds can be seen in Table 3.

ADMET Pharmacokinetic Prediction Results Active Compounds of Papaya Leaves (*Carica papaya*) with pKCSM Online Tool

Prediction of pharmacokinetic properties was carried out to predict ADMET parameters, namely absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion and toxicity using the pKCSM Online Tool. The results of ADMET pharmacokinetic predictions can be seen in Table 4.

Table 3. Physicochemical analysis the compounds of Papaya leaves (*Carica papaya*)

Active Compounds	CID	Formula	Molar mass (g/mol)	Log P	HBA	HBD	Molar Refractivity	Lipinski Rules
Ascorbic acid	54670067	C ₆ H ₈ O ₆	176.12	-2.60	6	4	35.12	X
Caffeic acid	689043	C ₉ H ₈ O ₄	180.16	0.70	4	3	47.16	✓
Carpaine	442630	C ₂₈ H ₅₀ N ₂ O ₄	478.71	3.75	6	2	146.37	X
Chymopapain	9002	C ₆ H ₆ O ₈ S ₂	270.24	-0.72	8	4	50.21	✓
Epicatechin	72276	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆	290.27	0.24	6	5	74.33	✓
Ferulic acid	445858	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄	194.18	1.00	4	2	51.63	✓
Gallic acid	370	C ₇ H ₆ O ₅	170.12	-0.16	5	4	39.47	X
Genistein	5280961	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	270.24	0.52	5	3	73.99	✓
Kaempferol	5280863	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	286.24	-0.03	6	4	76.01	✓
Lauric acid	3893	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ O ₂	200.32	3.15	2	1	61.57	✓
Linolenic acid	5280450	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	278.43	4.38	2	1	88.99	✓
Luteolin	5280445	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	286.24	-0.03	6	4	76.01	✓
Myricetin	5281672	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₈	318.24	-1.08	8	6	80.06	✓
Myristic acid	11005	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂	228.37	3.69	2	1	71.18	✓
Naringenin	439246	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₅	272.25	0.71	5	3	71.57	✓
Niacin	938	C ₅ H ₄ NCOOH	123.11	-1.13	3	1	31.20	✓
Nicotine	89594	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂	162.23	1.17	2	0	53.13	✓
Oleic acid	445639	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	282.46	4.57	2	1	89.94	✓
Palmitic-acid	985	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	256.42	4.19	2	1	80.80	✓
P-coumaric acid	637542	C ₉ H ₈ O ₃	164.16	1.28	3	2	45.13	✓
Quercetin	5280343	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	302.24	-0.56	7	5	78.03	✓
Rutin	5280805	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ O ₁₆	610.52	-3.89	16	10	141.38	X

Based on the ADMET prediction results in Table 4, it was found that the carpaine alkaloid group and the flavonoids naringenin, luteolin, and genistein were well absorbed in the intestine because they had an absorption value of more than 80%. The nine active compounds obtained logBB values <-1 so they did not penetrate the blood brain barrier (BBB). Kaempferol, myricetin, naringenin, luteolin, quercetin, and genistein act as inhibitors of CYP450, while routine does not activate and inhibits the CYP450 enzyme. These nine active compounds are not toxic or carcinogenic.

Table 4. ADMET Prediction of Papaya leaf phytochemical compounds (*Carica papaya*)

Active Compounds	Absorbtion		Distribution		Metabolism				Excretion	Toxicity	
	Intestinal absorption (%)	Caco2 Permeability (%)	V _{dss} (Log L/Kg)	BBB (log BB)	CYP 2D6 substrat	CYP 3A4 substrat	CYP 2D6 inhibitor	CYP 3A4 inhibitor	Total Clearance (log ml/min/kg)	Hepatotoxic	AMES
Ascorbic acid	39.154	-1.556	0.825	-0.985	No	No	No	No	0.631	No	No
Caffeic acid	69.407	-2.33	0.529	-0.647	No	No	No	No	0.508	No	No
Carpaine	92.276	-4.617	0.403	-0.355	No	Yes	No	No	0.897	No	No
Chymopapain	6.085	-2.892	0.423	-1.409	No	No	No	No	0.558	Yes	No
Epicatechin	68.829	-3.117	0.235	-1.054	No	No	No	No	0.183	No	No
Ferulic acid	93.685	-2.817	0.343	-0.239	No	No	No	No	0.623	No	No
Gallic acid	43.374	-2.56	0.617	-1.102	No	No	No	No	0.518	No	No
Genistein	93.387	-3.595	0.087	-0.71	No	No	No	No	0.151	No	No
Kaempferol	74.29	-3.04	0.178	-0.939	No	No	No	No	0.477	No	No
Lauric acid	93.379	-4.181	0.26	0.057	No	No	No	No	1.623	No	No
Luteolin	81.13	-3.094	0.168	-0.907	No	No	No	No	0.495	No	No
Myricetin	65.93	-2.915	0.238	-1.493	No	No	No	No	0.422	No	No
Myristic acid	92.691	-4.952	0.171	-0.027	No	No	No	No	1.693	No	No
Naringenin	91.31	-3.224	0.064	-0.578	No	No	No	No	0.06	No	No
Niacin	94.099	-2.134	0.776	-0.323	No	No	No	No	0.652	No	No
Nicotine	95.867	-0.872	0.628	0.208	No	No	No	No	0.86	Yes	No
Oleic acid	91.823	-5.924	0.052	-0.168	No	Yes	No	No	1.884	No	No
Palmitic-acid	92.004	-5.562	0.101	-0.111	No	Yes	No	No	1.763	No	No
P-coumaric acid	93.494	-2.378	0.428	-0.225	No	No	No	No	0.662	No	No
Quercetin	77.207	-2.925	0.206	-1.098	No	No	No	No	0.407	No	No
Rutin	23.446	-2.892	0.187	-1.899	No	No	No	No	-0.369	No	No

The affinity of the active compound for the target protein is determined by two indicators, namely free energy (ΔG) and the percentage of amino acid residue similarities. The parameter that measures the conformational stability between the ligand and the receptor is the free binding energy, which is abbreviated as ΔG . In this process, the ligand and receptor interact and reach the lowest energy, causing the molecule to be in a stable state. The lower the ΔG , the more stable the conformation produced by the binding between the ligand and the receptor. The smaller ΔG , the higher the affinity. The greater the percentage of binding similarities between the active compound and amino acid residues to the target protein compared to the control, the more stable the bond [2]. Test ligands that have amino acid residues close to the native ligand (control) indicate that the ligand has similar activity to the control [11].

The active compounds in papaya leaves (*Carica papaya*) that meet the Lipinski criteria are naringenin, kaempferol, luteolin, myricetin, quercetin, genistein, epicatechin. Because this compound meets the Lipinski criteria, which means the compound has water-soluble properties and can be easily absorbed through the intestine. However, some compounds such as routine and carpaine do not meet the Lipinski criteria so they do not penetrate cell membranes and are not easily absorbed in the intestine.

The active compounds of papaya leaves (*Carica papaya*) such as carpaine, naringenin, luteolin, and genistein are predicted to have good bioavailability if given via the oral route. However, in vivo research

is needed to assess its toxicity and bioactivity capabilities. It was proven that the active compound of papaya leaves has an antihypertensive effect on mice. Papaya's active compounds such as flavonoids have been proven to have the ability to increase NO production in endothelial cells. Where increasing NO production will cause vasodilation of blood vessels so that hypertension does not occur.

The free bond energy (ΔG) and percentage of amino acid residue equation of active compounds of papaya leaves on $\beta 1$ adrenergic receptor were myricetin (ΔG -9.3 kcal/mol, amino acid residue equation 66%), linoleic acid (-6.8, 66%) and ferulic acid (-7.6, 66%). As for phenylalanine hydrolase receptor the values of carpaine (ΔG -8.5 kcal/mol, amino acid residue equation 0%) were obtained. The antihypertensive mechanism of papaya leaves could be mediated by $\beta 1$ adrenergic receptor because the affinity level of its active substances to $\beta 1$ adrenergic receptor greater than phenylalanine hydrolase receptor.

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